

The Gourava Index of Four Operations on Graphs

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Abstract: Molecular descriptor are major in the study of QSAR/QSPR. There are numerous importance of graph theory in the field of structural chemistry. In the present paper, we study the Gourava index of four operation on graphs.

Key Words: Gourava index, Zagreb index, graph operations.

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§1. Introduction

Let \mathcal{G} denotes the collection entire graphs. A mapping $T : \mathcal{G} \rightarrow R$ is called a topological index, if for every graph H isomorphic to G , $T(G) = T(H)$. In chemical graph theory, topological indices have several applications in isomer discrimination, QSAR/QSPR investigation, pharmaceutical drug design and many more [5]. There are few important class of topological indices that are extensively studied by a number of researchers. Out of these topological indices, the first and second Zagreb indices, first appeared in a topological structure for the total π -energy of conjugated molecules, were introduced by Gutman et.al., in [8].

The first and second Zagreb indices [3] of a molecular graph G are defined as

$$M_1(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [d(u) + d(v)].$$

and

$$M_2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [d(u)d(v)].$$

Motivated by the definitions of the Zagreb indices and their wide applications, V. R. Kulli [10], introduced the first Gourava index of a molecular graph as follows.

The first Gourava index of a graph G is defined as

$$GO_1(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [d(u) + d(v) + d(u)d(v)].$$

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Figure 1: Graph G, H and $G +_F H$

The cartesian product is an important method to construct a ample graph and play vital role in the design and analysis the network. The cartesian product of two connected graphs G and H , which is denoted by $G \square H$, is a graph such that the set of vertices is $V(G) \square V(H)$ and two vertices (p_1, q_1) and (p_2, q_2) of $G \square H$ are adjacent if and only if $p_1 = p_2$ and q_1 is adjacent with q_2 in H otherwise $q_1 = q_2$ and p_1 is adjacent with p_2 in G . Let G be a graph with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$, there are four related graphs as follows:

For any connected graph G , define four operator graphs $S(G)$, $T(G)$, $Q(G) = T_1(G)$ and $R(G) = T_2(G)$ as follows:

- $S(G)$ is the graph obtained by inserting an additional vertex in each edge of G , i.e., replacing each edge of G by a path of length 2 ([1, 18]).
- The total graph $T(G)$ of a graph G is the graph whose vertex set $V \cup E$, with two vertices of $T(G)$ being adjacent if and only if the corresponding elements of G are adjacent or incident ([14]).
- $Q(G)$ is the graph obtained by inserting a new vertex into each edge of G , then joining with edges those pairs of new vertices on adjacent edges of G , by a new edge ([15]).
- $R(G)$ is the graph obtained by adding a new vertex corresponding to each edge of G , then joining each new vertex to the end vertices of the corresponding edge ([15]).

Suppose that G and H are two connected graphs. M. Eliasi, B. Taeri [6] introduced four new operations named as F-sum graphs, on these graphs that are based on S, T_2, T_1, T as follows.

Let F be one of the symbols S, T_2, T_1 or T . The F -sum denoted by $G +_F H$ of graphs G and H , is a graph with the set of vertices $V(G +_F H) = (V(G) \cup E(G)) \times V(H)$ and (p_1, p_2)

$(q_1, q_2) \in E(G +_F H)$, if and only if $p_1 = p_2 \in V(G)$ and $q_1 q_2 \in E(H)$ or $q_1 = q_2$ and $(p_1, p_2) \in E(F(G))$.

Throughout this paper, we consider only simple, connected, finite and undirected graphs. For a graph G , the order and the size of graph are denoted as n_G and e_G respectively.

In mathematical chemistry, graph operations act as a very essential role, viz., as some chemically interesting graphs can be derived from some simpler graphs by operations on graphs.

In [4], H. Deng et al. computed the first and second Zagreb indices for graph operations $S(G)$, $R(G)$, $Q(G)$ and $T(G)$. Here, we extend this study by investigate the Gourava index of four operation on graphs. Investigators need to study more details on calculating topological indices of graph operations can be refer [2, 7, 9, 11, 12, 16, 17, 19].

§2. The Gourava Index of F-Sum of Graphs

In this section, we discuss main results of Gourava index of F-sum of graphs.

Theorem 2.1 *Let G and H be two connected graphs. Then,*

$$GO_1(G +_s H) = n_H GO_1(G) + n_G GO_1(H) + e_H M_1(G) + 2e_G M_1(H) + 8n_H e_G + 12e_H e_G.$$

Proof From the definition of Gourava index,

$$\begin{aligned} GO_1(G +_s H) &= \sum_{(p_1, q_1)(p_2, q_2) \in E(G +_s H)} [d_{G +_s H}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G +_s H}(p_2, q_2) \\ &\quad + d_{G +_s H}(p_1, q_1)d_{G +_s H}(p_2, q_2)] \\ &= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} \sum_{q_1 q_2 \in E(H)} [d_{G +_s H}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G +_s H}(p_1, q_2) \\ &\quad + d_{G +_s H}(p_1, q_1)d_{G +_s H}(p_1, q_2)] \\ &\quad + \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{p_1 p_2 \in E(S(G))} [d_{G +_s H}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G +_s H}(p_1, q_2) \\ &\quad + d_{G +_s H}(p_1, q_1)d_{G +_s H}(p_1, q_2)] \\ &= I_1 + I_2, \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where I_1, I_2 are the sums of the above terms, in order.

For vertex $\forall p_1 \in V(G)$ and $q_1 q_2 \in E(H)$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} \sum_{q_1 q_2 \in E(H)} [d_G(p_1) + d_H(q_1) + d_G(p_1) + d_H(q_2) \\ &\quad + [d_G(p_1) + d_H(q_1)][d_G(p_1) + d_H(q_2)]] \\ &= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} \sum_{q_1 q_2 \in E(H)} [2d_G(p_1) + d_H(q_1) + d_H(q_2) + d_G^2(p_1) + d_G(p_1)[d_H(q_1) + d_H(q_2)] \\ &\quad + d_H(q_1)d_H(q_2)] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} [2e_H d_G(p_1) + M_1(H) + e_H d_G^2(p_1) + d_G(p_1)M_1(H) + M_2(H)] \\
&= 4e_H e_G + n_G G O_1(H) + e_H M_1(G) + 2e_G M_1(H).
\end{aligned}$$

For edge $\forall p_1 p_2 \in E(S(G))$, where the vertex $p_1 \in V(G)$, $p_2 \in V(S(G)) - V(G)$ and $q_1 \in V(H)$, since $|E(S(G))| = 2|E(G)|$,

$$\begin{aligned}
I_2 &= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{p_1 p_2 \in E(S(G))} [d_{S(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_1) + d_{S(G)}(p_2) \\
&\quad + [d_{S(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_1)]d_{S(G)}(p_2)] \\
&= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} [G O_1(S(G)) + 2e_G d_H(q_1) + 2e_G d_H(q_1)] \\
&= n_H G O_1(S(G)) + 8e_H e_G
\end{aligned}$$

We know that, $M_1 S(G) = M_1(G) + 4e_G$ and $M_2 S(G) = M_2(G) + 4e_G$. Therefore,

$$G O_1(S(G)) = G O_1(G) + 8e_G \quad \text{and} \quad I_2 = n_H G O_1(G) + 8n_H e_G + 8e_H e_G.$$

Substituting I_1 and I_2 in (1) we get required result

$$G O_1(G +_s H) = n_H G O_1(G) + n_G G O_1(H) + e_H M_1(G) + 2e_G M_1(H) + 8n_H e_G + 12e_H e_G. \quad \square$$

Theorem 2.2 *Let G and H be two connected graphs. Then,*

$$\begin{aligned}
G O_1(G +_{T_1} H) &= n_G G O_1(H) + 5e_H M_1(G) + 3e_G M_1(H) + 2n_H M_1(G) + 2e_G n_H M_1(G) \\
&\quad + 10e_H e_G + n_H \sum_{\substack{u_i u_j \in E(G), \\ u_j u_k \in E(G)}} [d_G(u_i)[1 + d_G(u_k)] + d_G(u_k)[1 + d_G(u_j)] \\
&\quad + d_G(u_j)[d_G(u_i) + d_G(u_j)]
\end{aligned}$$

Proof Consider

$$\begin{aligned}
G O_1(G +_{T_1} H) &= \sum_{(p_1, q_1)(p_2, q_2) \in E(G +_{T_1} H)} [d_{G +_{T_1} H}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G +_{T_1} H}(p_2, q_2) \\
&\quad + d_{G +_{T_1} H}(p_1, q_1)d_{G +_{T_1} H}(p_2, q_2)] \\
&= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} \sum_{q_1 q_2 \in E(H)} [d_{G +_{T_1} H}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G +_{T_1} H}(p_1, q_2) \\
&\quad + d_{G +_{T_1} H}(p_1, q_1)d_{G +_{T_1} H}(p_1, q_2)] \\
&\quad + \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{p_1 p_2 \in E(T_1(G))} [d_{G +_{T_1} H}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G +_{T_1} H}(p_2, q_1) \\
&\quad + d_{G +_{T_1} H}(p_1, q_1)d_{G +_{T_1} H}(p_2, q_1)].
\end{aligned}$$

The edge set $E(T_1(G))$ split in to $E(S(G))$ and $E(L(G))$. Let $E(T_1(G)) = \alpha_1$, $V(G) = \beta$,

$V(T_1(G)) - V(G) = \gamma_1$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
GO_1(G +_{T_1} H) &= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} \sum_{q_1 q_2 \in E(H)} [d_{G+T_1 H}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G+T_1 H}(p_1, q_2) \\
&\quad + d_{G+T_1 H}(p_1, q_1)d_{G+T_1 H}(p_1, q_2)] \\
&\quad + \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{p_1 p_2 \in \alpha_1, \\ p_1 \in \beta, \\ p_2 \in \gamma_1}} [d_{G+T_1 H}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G+T_1 H}(p_2, q_1) \\
&\quad + d_{G+T_1 H}(p_1, q_1)d_{G+T_1 H}(p_2, q_1)] \\
&\quad + \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{p_1 p_2 \in \alpha_1, \\ p_1, p_2 \in \gamma_1}} [d_{G+T_1 H}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G+T_1 H}(p_2, q_1) \\
&\quad + d_{G+T_1 H}(p_1, q_1)d_{G+T_1 H}(p_2, q_1)] \\
&= J_1 + J_2 + J_3, \tag{2}
\end{aligned}$$

where J_1, J_2, J_3 are the sums of the above terms, in order

$$\begin{aligned}
J_1 &= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} \sum_{q_1 q_2 \in E(H)} [2d_{T_1(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_1) + d_H(q_2) \\
&\quad + [d_{T_1(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_1)][d_{T_1(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_2)]] \\
&= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} \sum_{q_1 q_2 \in E(H)} [2d_{T_1(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_1) + d_H(q_2) + d_{T_1(G)}^2(p_1) + d_{T_1(G)}(p_1)d_H(q_2) \\
&\quad + d_H(q_1)d_H(q_2) + d_{T_1(G)}(p_1)d_H(q_1)] \\
&= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} [2e_H d_G(p_1) + GO_1(H) + e_H d_G^2(p_1) + d_G(p_1)d_H(q_2) + d_G(p_1)d_H(q_1)] \\
&= n_G GO_1(H) + e_H M_1(G) + e_G M_1(H) + 2e_H e_G.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
J_2 &= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{p_1 p_2 \in \alpha_1, \\ p_1 \in \beta, \\ p_2 \in \gamma_1}} [[d_{T_1(G)}(p_1) + 2d_H(q_1) + d_{T_1(G)}(p_2)] \\
&\quad + [d_{T_1(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_1)][d_{T_1(G)}(p_2) + d_H(q_1)]] \\
&= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{p_1 p_2 \in \alpha_1, \\ p_1 \in \beta, \\ p_2 \in \gamma_1}} [[d_G(p_1) + 2d_H(q_1) + d_{T_1(G)}(p_2)] \\
&\quad + [d_G(p_1) + d_H(q_1)][d_{T_1(G)}(p_2) + d_H(q_1)]] \\
&= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{p_1 p_2 \in \alpha_1, \\ p_1 \in \beta, \\ p_2 \in \gamma_1}} [d_G(p_1) + 2d_H(q_1) + d_{T_1(G)}(p_2) + d_G(p_1)d_{T_1(G)}(p_2) \\
&\quad + d_G(p_1)d_H(q_1) + d_H(q_1)d_{T_1(G)}(p_2) + d_H^2(q_1)]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} [d_G(p_1)[d_G(p_1) + 2d_H(q_1) + d_G(p_1)d_H(q_1) + d_H^2(q_1)]] \\
&\quad + \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{p_1 p_2 \in \alpha_1, \\ p_1 \in \beta, \\ p_2 \in \gamma_1}} [d_{T_1(G)}(p_2) + d_G(p_1)d_{T_1(G)}(p_2) + d_H(q_1)d_{T_1(G)}(p_2)].
\end{aligned}$$

We observe that for $p_2 \in V(T_1(G)) - V(G)$, $d_{T_1(G)}(p_2) = d_G(w_i) + d_G(w_j)$, where $p_2 = w_i w_j \in E(G)$. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}
J_2 &= n_H M_1(G) + 8e_H e_G + 2e_H M_1(G) + 2e_G M_1(H) \\
&\quad + \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{w_i w_j \in E(G)} [d_G(w_i) + d_G(w_j) + d_G(p_1)[d_G(w_i) + d_G(w_j)] \\
&\quad + d_H(q_1)[d_G(w_i) + d_G(w_j)]] \\
&= 2n_H M_1(G) + 8e_H e_G + 4e_H M_1(G) + 2e_G M_1(H) + 2e_G n_H M_1(G).
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
J_3 &= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{p_1 p_2 \in \alpha_1, p_1, p_2 \in \gamma_1} [[d_{T_1(G)}(p_1) + d_{T_1(G)}(p_2)] + [d_{T_1(G)}(p_1)d_{T_1(G)}(p_2)]] \\
&= n_H \sum_{\substack{u_i u_j \in E(G), \\ u_j u_k \in E(G)}} [[d_G(u_i) + d_G(u_j) + d_G(u_j) + d_G(u_k)] \\
&\quad + [d_G(u_i) + d_G(u_j)][d_G(u_j) + d_G(u_k)]] \\
&= n_H \sum_{\substack{u_i u_j \in E(G), \\ u_j u_k \in E(G)}} [d_G(u_i)[1 + d_G(u_k)] + d_G(u_k)[1 + d_G(u_j)] + d_G(u_j)[d_G(u_i) + d_G(u_j)]] .
\end{aligned}$$

Adding J_1, J_2, J_3 in (2) we get desired result. \square

Theorem 2.3 *Let G and H be two connected graphs. Then,*

$$\begin{aligned}
GO_1(G +_{T_2} H) &= 4n_H GO_1(G) + GO_1(H) + 8e_H M_1(G) + 5e_G M_1(H) + 6n_H M_1(G) \\
&\quad + 4n_H M_2(G) + 24e_H e_G + 4n_H e_G
\end{aligned}$$

Proof We know that,

$$\begin{aligned}
GO_1(G +_{T_2} H) &= \sum_{(p_1, q_1)(p_2, q_2) \in E(G +_{T_2} H)} [d_{G +_{T_2} H}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G +_{T_2} H}(p_2, q_2) \\
&\quad + d_{G +_{T_2} H}(p_1, q_1)d_{G +_{T_2} H}(p_1, q_2)] \\
&= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} \sum_{q_1 q_2 \in E(H)} [d_{G +_{T_2} H}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G +_{T_2} H}(p_1, q_2) \\
&\quad + d_{G +_{T_2} H}(p_1, q_1)d_{G +_{T_2} H}(p_1, q_2)] \\
&\quad + \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{p_1 p_2 \in E(T_1(G))} [d_{G +_{T_2} H}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G +_{T_2} H}(p_2, q_1) \\
&\quad + d_{G +_{T_2} H}(p_1, q_1)d_{G +_{T_2} H}(p_2, q_1)]
\end{aligned}$$

$$= K_1 + K_2, \quad (3)$$

where K_1 and K_1 are the sums of the above terms, in order

$$\begin{aligned} K_1 &= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} \sum_{q_1, q_2 \in E(H)} [2d_{T_2(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_1) + d_H(q_2) \\ &\quad + d_{T_2(G)}^2(p_1) + d_{T_2(G)}(p_1)[d_H(q_1) + d_H(q_2)] + d_H(q_1)d_H(q_2)] \\ &= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} \sum_{q_1, q_2 \in E(H)} [4d_G(p_1) + d_H(q_1) + d_H(q_2) \\ &\quad + 4d_G^2(p_1) + 2d_G(p_1)[d_H(q_1) + d_H(q_2)] + d_H(q_1)d_H(q_2)] \\ &= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} [4e_H d_G(p_1) + GO_1(H) + 4e_H d_G^2(p_1) + 2d_G(p_1)M_1(H)] \\ &= 8e_H e_G + GO_1(H) + 4e_H M_1(G) + 4e_G M_1(H) \end{aligned} \quad (3a)$$

for edge $\forall p_1 p_2 \in E(T_2(G))$ and vertex $q_1 \in V(H)$. Here we denote $E(T_2(G)) = \alpha_2$, $V(G) = \beta$, $V(T_2(G)) - V(G) = \gamma_2$.

$$\begin{aligned} K_2 &= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{p_1 p_2 \in E(T_2(G))} [d_{G+T_2 H}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G+T_2 H}(p_2, q_1) \\ &\quad + d_{G+T_2 H}(p_1, q_1)d_{G+T_2 H}(p_2, q_1)] \\ &\quad + \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{p_1 p_2 \in \alpha_2, \\ p_1 \in \beta, \\ p_2 \in \gamma_2}} [d_{G+T_2 H}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G+T_2 H}(p_2, q_1) + d_{G+T_2 H}(p_1, q_1)d_{G+T_2 H}(p_2, q_1)] \\ &= K_3 + K_4 \end{aligned} \quad (3b).$$

for $\forall q_1 \in V(H)$ and edge $p_1 p_2 \in E(T_2(G))$ if and only if $p_1 p_2 \in E(G)$.

$$\begin{aligned} K_3 &= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{p_1 p_2 \in E(G)} [d_{G+T_2(G)H}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G+T_2(G)H}(p_2, q_1) \\ &\quad + d_{G+T_2(G)H}(p_1, q_1)d_{G+T_2(G)H}(p_2, q_1)] \\ &= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{p_1 p_2 \in E(G)} [d_{T_2(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_1) + d_{T_2(G)}(p_2) + d_H(q_1) \\ &\quad + [d_{T_2(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_1)][d_{T_2(G)}(p_2) + d_H(q_1)]] \\ &= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{p_1 p_2 \in E(G)} [2d_G(p_1) + 2d_H(q_1) + 2d_G(p_2) + 4d_G(p_1)d_G(p_2) \\ &\quad + 2d_G(p_1)d_H(q_1) + 2d_H(q_1)d_G(p_2) + d_H^2(q_1)] \\ &= 4n_H GO_1(G) + 4e_H M_1(G) + e_G M_1(H) + 4n_H M_2(G) + 4e_H e_G. \end{aligned}$$

Since we have $d_{T_2(G)}(p_1) = 2d_G(p_1)$ for each vertex $p_1 \in V(G)$ and $d_{T_2}(p_2) = 2$ for each vertex $p_2 \in V(T_2(G)) - V(G)$,

$$\begin{aligned}
K_4 &= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{p_1 p_2 \in \alpha_2, \\ p_1 \in \beta, \\ p_2 \in \gamma_2}} [d_{T_2(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_1) + d_{T_2(G)}(p_2) \\
&\quad + [d_{T_2(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_1)]d_{T_2(G)}(p_2)] \\
&= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{p_1 p_2 \in \alpha_2, \\ p_1 \in \beta, \\ p_2 \in \gamma_2}} [d_{T_2(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_1) + d_{T_2(G)}(p_2) \\
&\quad + d_{T_2(G)}(p_1)d_{T_2(G)}(p_2) + d_H(q_1)d_{T_2(G)}(p_2)] \\
&= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{p_1 p_2 \in \alpha_2, \\ p_1 \in \beta, \\ p_2 \in \gamma_2}} [6d_G(p_1) + 3d_H(q_1) + 2] \\
&= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} d_G(p_1) [6d_G(p_1) + 3d_H(q_1) + 2] \\
&= 6n_H M_1(G) + 12e_G e_H + 4n_H e_G.
\end{aligned}$$

Adding K_3 and K_4 and substitute in (3b) we get

$$4n_H GO_1(G) + 16e_{HeG} + 6n_H M_1(G) + 4e_H M_1(G) + e_G M_1(H) + 4n_H M_2(G) + 4n_H e_G. \quad (3c)$$

Substitute (3a) and (3c) in (3) we get desired results.

$$\begin{aligned}
GO_1(G +_{T_2} H) &= 4n_H GO_1(G) + GO_1(H) + 8e_H M_1(G) + 5e_G M_1(H) + 6n_H M_1(G) \\
&\quad + 4n_H M_2(G) + 24e_{HeG} + 4n_H e_G.
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

Theorem 2.4 *Let G and H be two connected graphs. Then,*

$$\begin{aligned}
GO_1(G +_T H) &= 4n_H GO_1(G) + n_G GO_1(H) + 12e_H M_1(G) + 6e_G M_1(H) \\
&\quad + 2n_H M_1(G) + e_G M_2(H) + 8e_G M_1(G) + 20e_{HeG} \\
&\quad + n_H \sum_{\substack{q_i q_j \in E(G), \\ q_j q_k \in E(G)}} [d_G(q_i) + 2d_G(q_j) + d_G(q_k) \\
&\quad + [d_G(q_i) + d_G(q_j)][d_G(q_j) + d_G(q_k)]]
\end{aligned}$$

Proof Let

$$\begin{aligned}
GO_1(G +_T H) &= \sum_{(p_1, q_1)(p_2, q_2) \in E(G+TH)} [d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G+TH}(p_2, q_2) \\
&\quad + d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_1)d_{G+TH}(p_2, q_2)]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} \sum_{q_1, q_2 \in E(H)} [d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_2) \\
&\quad + d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_1)d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_2)] \\
&\quad + \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{p_1, p_2 \in E(T(G))} [d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G+TH}(p_2, q_1) \\
&\quad + d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_1)d_{G+TH}(p_2, q_1)].
\end{aligned}$$

Note that $E(T(G)) = E(G) \cup E(S(G)) \cup E(L(G))$. We get that

$$\begin{aligned}
&GO_1(G+TH) \\
&= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} \sum_{q_1, q_2 \in E(H)} [d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_2) + d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_1)d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_2)] \\
&\quad + \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{(p_1, p_2) \in E(T(G)), \\ (p_1, p_2) \in V(G)}} [d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G+TH}(p_2, q_1) + d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_1)d_{G+TH}(p_2, q_1)] \\
&\quad + \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{(p_1, p_2) \in \alpha_3, \\ p_1 \in \beta, \\ p_2 \in \gamma_3}} [d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G+TH}(p_2, q_1) + d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_1)d_{G+TH}(p_2, q_1)] \\
&\quad + \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{(p_1, p_2) \in \alpha_3, \\ (p_1, p_2) \in \gamma_3}} [d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G+TH}(p_2, q_1) + d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_1)d_{G+TH}(p_2, q_1)] \\
&= L_1 + L_2 + L_3 + L_4, \tag{4}
\end{aligned}$$

where L_1, L_2, L_3, L_4 are the sums of the above terms, in order

$$\begin{aligned}
L_1 &= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} \sum_{q_1, q_2 \in E(H)} [2d_{T(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_1) + d_H(q_2) \\
&\quad + [d_{T(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_1)][d_{T(G)}(p_1)d_H(q_2)]] \\
&= \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} \sum_{q_1, q_2 \in E(H)} [4d_G(p_1) + d_H(q_1) + d_H(q_2) + 4d_G^2(p_1) + 2d_G(p_1)d_H(q_1)] \\
&\quad + 2d_G(p_1)d_H(q_2) + d_H(q_1)d_H(q_2) \\
&= n_G GO_1(H) + 4e_H M_1(G) + 4e_G M_1(H) + 8e_G e_H.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
L_2 &= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{p_1, p_2 \in \alpha_3, p_1, p_2 \in \beta} [d_{T(G)}(p_1) + 2d_H(q_1) + d_{T(G)}(p_2) \\
&\quad + [d_{T(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_1)][d_{T(G)}(p_2)d_H(q_1)]] \\
&= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{p_1, p_2 \in E(G)} [2d_G(p_1) + 2d_G(p_2) + 2d_H(q_1) + d_H^2(q_1) + 2d_G(p_2)d_H(q_1) \\
&\quad + 4d_G(p_1)d_G(p_2) + 2d_G(p_1)d_H(q_1)] \\
&= 2n_H GO_1(G) + 4e_H M_1(G) + e_G M_2(H) + 2n_H M_2(G) + 4e_G e_H.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
L_3 &= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{p_1 p_2 \in \alpha_3, \\ p_1 \in \beta, \\ p_2 \in \gamma_3}} [d_{T(G)}(p_1) + d_{T(G)}(p_2) + 2d_H(q_1) \\
&\quad + [d_{T(G)}(p_1) + d_H(q_1)][d_{T(G)}(p_2)d_H(q_1)]] \\
&= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{p_1 \in V(G)} [d_G(p_1)2d_G(p_1) + d_H(q_1) + d_H(q_1) + d_G(p_1)d_H(q_1) + d_H^2(q_1)] \\
&\quad + \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{p_1 p_2 \in \alpha_3, \\ p_1 \in \beta, \\ p_2 \in \gamma_3}} [d_{T(G)}(p_2) + 2d_G(p_1)d_{T(G)}(p_2) + d_H(q_1)d_{T(G)}(p_2)].
\end{aligned}$$

Note that $p_2 \in V(T(G)) - V(G)$, $d_{T(G)}(p_2) = d_G(p) + d_G(q)$ where $p_2 = pq \in E(G)$, we further get that

$$\begin{aligned}
L_3 &= 2n_H M_1(G) + 4e_H M_1(G) + 2e_G M_1(H) + 8e_H e_G \\
&\quad + \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{p_1 \in \beta, \\ p_2 \in \gamma_3}} [(d_G(p) + d_G(q)) + 2d_G(p_1)(d_G(p) + d_G(q)) + d_H(q_1)(d_G(p) + d_G(q))] \\
&= 2n_H M_1(G) + 4e_H M_1(G) + 2e_G M_1(H) + 2n_H M_1(G) + 8e_G M_1(G) + 4e_H M_1(G) \\
&= 4n_H M_1(G) + 4e_H M_1(G) + 8e_G M_1(G) + 2e_G M_1(H) + 8e_H e_G.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
L_4 &= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{(p_1, p_2) \in \gamma_3} [d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_1) + d_{G+TH}(p_2, q_1) + d_{G+TH}(p_1, q_1)d_{G+TH}(p_2, q_1)] \\
&= \sum_{q_1 \in V(H)} \sum_{\substack{p_1, \\ p_2 \in \gamma_3}} [d_{T(G)}(p_1) + d_{T(G)}(p_2) + d_{T(G)}(p_1)d_{T(G)}(p_2)] \\
&= n_H \sum_{q_i q_j \in E(G), q_j q_k \in E(G)} [(d_G(q_i) + d_G(q_j)) + (d_G(q_j) + d_G(q_k)) \\
&\quad + [d_G(q_i) + d_G(q_j)][d_G(q_j) + d_G(q_k)]]
\end{aligned}$$

Adding L_1, L_2, L_3, L_4 in (4) we get required result. \square

§3. Conclusion

In this paper, we obtain explicit expression for the Gourava index of four operation on graphs in terms of first Zagreb and second Zagreb index.

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